

Research

Neoliberal ideology in O-levels English language textbooks in Pakistan

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Abstract: The current study explored the neoliberal ideology in O-levels English textbooks, published by Oxford University Press, taught in elite schools of Pakistan. Using Fairclough's three-dimensional model of Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) (1989, 2002, 2015) as a theoretical and analytical framework, neoliberal themes in two the textbooks were analyzed. The results show that both the textbooks were rife with neoliberal ideological themes of marketization, self-entrepreneurship, celebrity and popular culture, competition, and individualism. These market-based themes promote a culture of excessive competition and turn every act into transaction. There is a need to explore this area of research further in Pakistani context and teachers need to be more critical of the messages ingrained in these imported textbooks being transmitted to the students.

Keywords: Neoliberal themes, O-levels English textbooks, CDA

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Introduction

The widespread usage of English language as a global lingua franca has elevated its standing as a "global" language. English is utilized for communication, but more significantly, it has established itself as a language of instruction. Since English is employed as a means of knowledge transfer in fields like art, science, technology, and business, it has achieved a stature that no other language has (Babaii et al, 2018). Because of this, the need for English instruction and learning has been growing over time. In fact, a lot of EFL textbooks are produced to satisfy the various demands of a global community. These textbooks have a cultural slant because they are primarily published by English-speaking nations.

The issue that needs a careful examination is neoliberalism in ELT and its strategies for justifying its presence through language instruction (Babaii et al, 2018). Along with the entry of western cultural values, neoliberal ideals in ELT have also become a source of concern for linguists (Daghigh et al, 2020). Therefore, the current study's objective is to investigate and evaluate how neoliberal values are represented in O-level textbooks of grade 9 and 10. As a Western-adopted

economic school of thinking, neoliberalism has influenced not just economics but also social and private spheres of life. Throughout the history of English's globalisation, ELT has been employed as a tool to increase the ideology of power and influence held by core nations. As a result, it is currently utilised to spread neoliberal values among the general public. This calls for a critical review of the materials utilized to indoctrinate the students with a foreign ideology, particularly in the Periphery countries that have different cultural values from the West.

Studies on EFL content that promotes ideological ideas and seeks to benefit powerful social groups have been undertaken in Pakistan (See: Rahman, 1995; 1998; Nayer and Hoodbhoy, 2003; Mahboob, 2009; Shah, 2016). There is, however, a dearth of studies that examine Neoliberal ideology in the context of Pakistan using critical discourse analysis. Future studies on the prevalence of neoliberal ideology in ELT materials and classroom instruction will benefit from the findings of this study. Neoliberal discourse allows for the investigation of the ideology's impact on students. The total effects of neoliberal discourse in ELT in Pakistan have never been examined due to a lack of study on critical analysis of this discourse. It is crucial for scholars, particularly those working in applied linguistics, to be skeptical of the rhetoric of strong beliefs that could result in a volatile classroom environment where competition replaces cooperation.

Literature review

Bourdieu and Passeron (1977) assert that textbooks are social reproduction tools designed to educate and acculturate future citizens into a society based on prevailing "macro-discourses." Textbooks do not necessarily include factual information; instead, they are the product of negotiations and agreements reached during social, political, and economic conflicts (Apple & Christian-Smith, 1991). According to Babaii and Sheikhi (2017, p. 248), textbooks are loaded with values and provide for an excellent study tool for analyzing ideological discourse. Thus, they provide for a good data source to study and explore neoliberal ideology.

The neoliberal ideology is reproduced and supported by contemporary ELT textbooks (Gray and Block, 2014, p. 45). According to Gray (2012), English language coursebooks encourage a connection between success and consumerism, which reinforces neoliberal ideology. Chun (2009) did research on English for Academic Purposes (EAP) intensive English programme. He discovered that the brochures on the website for getting admission in the program were being utilised to entice students to a high-end leisure lifestyle by using a multimodal analysis on the website and textbook used in the university programme. On the other hand, according to Holborow (2007), the textbook's emphasis on emotional intelligence and communication skills were expressly created to foster the development of successful entrepreneurs. Caring capitalism also predominated. Moreover, in his research, Gray (2012) had noticed that the neoliberal worldview is in line with the widespread usage of celebrities in teaching materials, particularly those pertaining to ELT. Similarly, based on a qualitative content analysis methodology, Copley (2017) examined the previous 40 years' worth of international ELT coursebooks. It was determined that throughout the early years (1975–1982), the emphasis was on finding cooperative solutions to issues that students and teachers encountered together. Controversial subjects were not avoided, and students were required to address them (p. 9). Modern ELT books, however, have changed their emphasis to a more constrained approach, replacing socially experienced problems and their solutions with individual entrepreneurship (p. 13).

According to Copley (2017), with the integration of the concept of human capital into language instruction, communication over time became understood as a transaction, and the neoliberal notion of the market and competitiveness assumed centre stage (Becker, 1983). Following the similar trend, Xiong et al. (2018) examined the neoliberal discourse in ELT textbooks that promotes learning English as a desirable linguistic cultural capital that is an individual and asocial experience that every individual can master if he is willing to buy it and that learning English is a monolingual and monocultural experience through a CDA-informed analysis of the pedagogic texts in the Chinese context (p. 11). In addition to it, Daghigh et al. (2020) did a thematic discourse analysis on locally and imported textbooks in Malaysia to assess how neoliberal values are portrayed in each. The researchers discovered that imported textbooks more fully

embodied neoliberal values than locally produced textbooks, and themes related to neoliberal core concepts of consumerism and material wealth were present in both types of textbooks, but celebrity and competitiveness-related content was missing from local textbooks in Malaysia (p. 14).

Moreover, in Serbia's private language school for unemployed students, Bori (2021) did critical ethnographic study while considering two English courses. The neoliberal biases were exposed by looking at students' views and behaviours surrounding the usage of English and by using global English textbooks rather than local textbooks. However, in Pakistan, there is a shortage of study on neoliberalism and its connections to neoliberal rhetoric in English language textbooks in Pakistan. Recent studies on the relationship between neoliberalism and language in Pakistan may be found in Manan (2021) and Shah et al. (2022 in press).

Research Methodology

Data collection source

The data for the current study has been taken from Oxford University Press (OUP) O-level English textbooks, which are used at the elite schools in Sindh province of Pakistan. The third editions of these two textbooks, "Oxford Progressive English-9" and "Oxford Progressive English-10," both written by Rachel Redford, released in 2016, have been used. Each Oxford Progressive English book has 10 total units. Each unit is broken down into a number of texts, with the OUP for grade-9 comprising 37 texts and the OUP for grade-10 containing 41 texts.

Fairclough's three-dimensional model as Theoretical and Analytical framework

Michael Halliday's Systemic Functional Linguistics served as the basis for Fairclough's CDA model. In order to increase public awareness, Fairclough's three-dimensional model seeks to deconstruct the oppressive power relations that are used through language. The three dimensions or levels of analysis included in this model are the micro-level (text), the meso-level (discourse), and the macro-level (social practise). The word-level analysis that takes place at the micro-level examines the syntax, word choice, and text structure. The description phase of analysis is what it is termed. Meso-level analysis is done on "text generation, dissemination, and consumption" and how social circumstances affect its variability (Fairclough 1992, p. 78). At this level, the intertextuality or interdiscursivity of the discourse is investigated. The interpretation step of analysis is what it is termed. The macro-level examination focuses on societal customs. The sociocultural context is a factor in text processing at this level. The explanation step of analysis is what it is called.

For the current study, the analytical categories which are suitable for the analysis of neoliberal ideology have been adopted in the present study. Fairclough's descriptive and interpretative stages are very comprehensive for analysis of textbooks, thus certain categories are omitted due to their irrelevance to the topic of neoliberal ideology.

Figure 1. Fairclough's three-dimensional model (1995)

Results and Discussion

Market is the foundation on which stands the whole setup of neoliberalism. For market, anything that has material importance is more valuable. People, including their skills and expertise are quantified through market logic of monetary profit and loss. The following excerpt 1 laments a sort of misfortune for a classical literary giant Charles Dickens because he could not earn the profit off his work like the writers of neoliberal era.

1. *Unfortunately for Dickens, however, copyright laws had not yet come into existence, and he earned not a single penny for all the hundreds of thousands of his novels sold in America. (Pg 21, book 9)*

The sentence begins with the adverb "unfortunately", which represents the text producer's representation of reality as one with disadvantage. Her evaluation of truth is based on negative assertion, revealing her unhappiness of the stated point. It is presupposed by the text producer that not earning a single penny is something that is upsetting, and thus puts Dickens at a losing end despite writing hundreds of thousands of books.

In the next excerpt 2, the market logic is obvious. In neoliberalism, even pets are valued for their monetary returns and their hand in their owner's popularity. The following excerpt is about the buffalo who earned its owner a lot of fortune and fame.

2. *Holmes is now an ambassador for the business and has helped to put the buffalo-meat business back on track. He's made an appearance in a five-star hotel, and had a small part in a film. He was even asked to be best bison" at a wedding! We've got photos of me saddled up on him. Oh yes, he's got a fine future-he's so popular now that he's got an agent. (Pg. 55, book 9)*

The agency of the text is being deliberately made unclear. Holmes is the name of the buffalo, which obviously cannot make decisions for itself. Yet, the text attributes the agency to the animal, thus hiding the real human agent behind the decision-making process. The human subject is the real agent who is using the animal for gaining success and popularity for itself.

Similarly, the excerpt 3 below clearly lays out the solution of an environmental disaster in the form of economic gain. The market exploitation of climate is visible in the text.

3. *The best solution seems to be efforts to turn what for many has become an affliction to an advantage by building up a market for mesquite products.* (Pg. 81, book 10)

The use of the adjective 'best' implies that there are other solutions possible as well, but they are not as good as the one provided by the text producer. The mental verb 'seems' shows that the evaluation of reality is portrayed as that of a possibility which the interpreters of the texts should consider. It is given as a commonsense assumption that 'an affliction' can be turned into 'an advantage' just by producing market for goods of a product that is wreaking havoc with environment of concerned people and their livelihood.

Popularity and fame play at the hands of market, which governs who gains the excessive attention and recognition and who does not. Following excerpt 4 is explicitly creating a dramatic background for the appearance of J.K. Rowling as a celebrity with monetary fortunes following her.

4. *Just before midnight, J.K. Rowling, the creator of Harry Potter, arrived at the castle in a black limousine and disappeared behind its ancient portals*.* (Pg. 21, book 10)

The beginning of the sentence contains the information that is considered most important. In the above excerpt 4 the text producer has created a dramatic impression out of the sentence to portray the person of J.K. Rowling as a celebrity figure by laying ground for her unusual stunt. The specific mention of 'black limousine' shows that the reality portrayed by the text producer is one in which a person possessing a branded car is worth every attention and fame.

Competition lies at the heart of neoliberal logic in which winners and losers are decided based on concrete gains and losses. Neoliberalism has affected the educational system as well in which students are evaluated based on their grades rather than real knowledge. Following excerpt 5 is a dialogue uttered by the parents of a child who has broken the norm of achieving 'high' grades and has actually acquired grades not considered worthy in the society.

5. *Until now he has always had A and B grades in his subjects, but this time he was not awarded any A grades. He even had two C grades which he has never had before. We are sure you will understand our concern.* (pg. 78, book 9)

By using the subordinate clause in which the main clause contains the part that is most important, the text producer has established that the child is 'competent', but something is wrong with him just because he has not achieved the same grades this time. The connector 'but' shows that it is unusual to the followed norm. The adverb 'even' is shown to portray the gravity of situation to be more persuasive. It is given as a common sense and mutual fact that this situation can be better understood by both the parents and the school's administration since grades are what define a student in a neoliberal educational setting.

This principle of competitiveness is further explained below in the excerpt 6 in which the text interpreters are taught the winner and loser approach of the neoliberal market.

6. *Most developments and changes have winners and loser. For example, land is cleared so that new houses can be built on it. Some of the winners are those who make money out of the building project, some of the losers are those whose homes had to be demolished to clear the land.* (Pg. 101, book 9)

The text begins with the adverb 'most' to show the text producer's evaluation of reality that almost all developments and changes have winners and losers. It is being conveyed that it is a commonsense understanding that almost no development can occur without someone losing in the end. This neoliberal principle of change and progress is further elaborated via an example in which gain is portrayed in the form of monetary benefit and so is the loss. Furthermore,

the modal verb 'had to' shows strong opinion of the text producer that it is a necessity to create homelessness for development of other important projects to happen.

Competitiveness is not only reinforced in the textbook through economic success but also by molding the mindset of learners through examples of their heroes. Following excerpt 7 is the dialogue between an interviewer who is himself a successful author and the interviewee who is a professional boxer who is showing an extreme competitive spirit to the audience.

7. *HK: Is it something about winning that's the turn on for you?*

AK: Yeah, it's about winning. I'm one of those guys who always have to keep winning. I'm like the hero. (Pg. 97, book 10)

The question is asked in a yes/no format to confirm or reject an opinion. It is presupposed by the interviewer that winning is a crucial stimulus for a player and he is thus confirming that presupposed notion. Amir Khan's reply is confirmation of the interviewer's notion. He further maintains that he 'has to' keep winning, using modality for assertiveness to show lack of choice on his part. He makes it clear that a hero never loses, thus, establishing the neoliberal value in which one's importance is only gauged by the concrete titles she has earned than anything else.

Analyzing further the concept of neoliberal competitiveness, the excerpt 8 shows bleak reality of South Korea's education system.

8. *But there is pressure to succeed and there is intense competition among students. Gaining a place in a good university is thought to dictate a student's entire future success in working life. People here are aware of the accusations that the country overworks its youth; nevertheless the transformation is nothing short of remarkable. (Pg. 122, book 10)*

The logical connector 'but' shows helplessness on the part of agents who find themselves bound to success in an insane educational competition. In a neoliberal world, one's working life predominates every other sphere of life to the point that everything boils down to success in career. This leads to excessive competition which is portrayed in the excerpt. The text producer presupposes that 'people' are aware of accusations on the country, using 'imaginative intertextuality' as a technique. However, this accusation is balanced by the text producer's expressive value of the connector 'nevertheless' which implies that tough competitive education system is working for the country, thus it is good.

Individualism and self-responsibility are the other two themes of neoliberal ideology. The competition has led to depending on oneself only without influence and help of anyone else. This theme of choosing for oneself and making one capable is predominant in both the textbooks. Following text is about grandparents and their value in one's life.

9. *He never chose for me, or told me what do, he just explained what he thought was right and wrong, and let me make up my own mind. (Pg. 154, book 10)*

This excerpt clearly stipulates the neoliberal notion of 'choice of an individual' over anything else. The sentence is in negation with strong negative form of 'never' that shows that something is impossible. The grandchild values his granddad for the fact that he does not invade his privacy. However, if he ever did, he would not have been in his grandson's good books for whom making decisions solely for oneself is paramount to his liberty.

This same notion of individualism and advantage for oneself is further strengthened in the excerpt 10. In neoliberal ideology one's success is solely measured based on what one can achieve for him or herself regardless of social consequences.

10. *No one can deny that finishing the MdS is an incredible accomplishment. But more importantly, you will walk away with a new slant on life-that you can achieve anything you set your mind to do.* (Pg. 52, book 10)

The excerpt 10 above begins with the indefinite pronoun 'no one' to establish that no person will reject the point that winning a race called MdS is an extremely important accomplishment. This is a method of making the text interpreters assent to the reality as viewed by the text producer as an established 'fact'. However, by using the connector 'but', the producer has elaborated his point to tell that more important than winning the race that benefits people in the form of charity, is what the race does for you as a person.

The same notion of individual development by taking responsibility of one's own success is maintained in the excerpt 11 below. Taking initiative and seeking risks lies at the core of competitive logic of neoliberal ideology.

Conclusion

The present study explored the presence of neoliberal ideology in O levels English textbooks of grade 9 and 10 published by Oxford University Press taught in Pakistan's elite schools. By employing Fairclough's three-dimensional model as a theoretical and analytical framework of CDA, the study found that neoliberal themes of marketization, competition, self-entrepreneurship, individualism, celebrity culture and fame were predominant in both the textbooks of O levels. Several researchers have investigated neoliberal themes in the context of ELT and language learning materials, including Chun (2009), Gray (2012), Copley (2017), Babaii et al. (2017) Xiong et al. (2018), Daghigh et al. (2020) and Bori (2021) in the international context following varying models of analysis and research methods. Similarly, in Pakistan, Manan (2021) and Shah et al, (2022, in press) conducted research on neoliberalism and its role in ELT, however, using different methods of analysis and contextual frameworks. Thus, the current study aimed at filling the gap in research in Applied Linguistics on neoliberal ideology and its dissemination through foreign imported O levels English textbooks using Critical Discourse Analysis.

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